

ISSN - 0975-2382

UPUEA ECONOMIC JOURNAL

A Biannual-Bilingual Double Blind Peer Reviewed Refereed Journal of Economics

Volume - 20 (B)

Conference No. 20 (Section 2&3)

09th-11th November 2024

20th ANNUAL NATIONAL CONFERENCE (09th - 11th November, 2024)

Demographic Transition and Social Sector Challenges in India :
Understanding Demographic Dynamics

Agricultural Growth, Rural Poverty, and Sustainable Development

India's External Sector Reforms and Challenges

Exploring Tourism Opportunities and Overcoming Challenges in Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation: A Global Challenge

Uttar Pradesh - Uttarakhand Economic Association (UPUEA)

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KIPM College of Management, GIDA, Gorakhpur, (U.P) India

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Analyzing Trade Trends to Shape India's Export Strategy with BRICS for the Next Decade

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ABSTRACT

This research paper focuses on examining the trade patterns between India and the BRICS nations over the past decade, paying special attention to key sectors, opportunities, and challenges. By analyzing trade data, the paper explores how India can refine its export strategy to strengthen its trade partnerships within the BRICS framework, especially with Russia.

This research is quantitative as it analyses the relation between India's bilateral trade from BRICS, special reference to Russia. It is descriptive in nature and based on secondary data sources as Ministry of Commerce and Industry database, World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF) etc.

Russia, as one of India's primary partners in defense, energy, and agriculture, holds significant potential for expanding trade cooperation in these and other sectors. Russia's abundant natural resources, combined with India's expanding manufacturing and technological expertise, present promising opportunities for cooperation. The paper offers strategic recommendations to improve India's export competitiveness and encourage long-term, sustainable trade relationships with BRICS countries, with a particular emphasis on Russia.

The findings highlight that building stronger trade relations with Russia provides economic benefits for India while also boosting its influence within the BRICS group which can give better position for the next decade of economic expansion.

Key words: BRICS, Export strategy, Trade trends, Opportunities

Introduction

India has been involved in trade relations with the BRICS countries since 2001. The acronym BRICS refers to Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa, forming a coalition of these five major economies. As these emerging economies continue to grow and reshape global trade dynamics, understanding past trade trends becomes essential for developing an effective export strategy. This

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paper analyzes the patterns of export growth, challenges, and opportunities within BRICS, helping India better position itself to take advantage of expanding markets, foster stronger economic ties, and secure a more influential role in global trade over the next decade.

The BRICS nations represent an important portion of global GDP and trade, making them critical partners for India's export goals. Each country within the group offers unique opportunities, from Russia's demand for pharmaceuticals and agricultural products to China's vast consumer market. However, challenges such as trade barriers, and economic slowdowns must also be considered when formulating India's export strategy. By tailoring its approach to the specific needs and conditions of each BRICS nation, India can strengthen its economic resilience, diversify its export markets, and ensure sustained growth in the world economy.

Overview of BRICS Economies

The BRICS nations represent a diverse group of economies with different strengths, challenges, and growth trajectories. This section provides a brief overview of each BRICS member.

Brazil is the largest economy in South America, characterized by its vast natural resources and a robust agricultural sector. The country is a major exporter of commodities such as soybeans, iron ore, and crude oil. However, Brazil has faced challenges, including economic instability, political turmoil, and infrastructural deficits. Despite these issues, Brazil remains an important trade partner for India, particularly in the agricultural and energy sectors.

Russia's economy is heavily reliant on natural resources, particularly oil and gas, making it a key player in global energy markets. India and Russia have historically maintained strong ties, especially in defense and energy sectors. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in diversifying trade beyond traditional commodities, with potential opportunities in pharmaceuticals, technology, and agricultural products.

India is the fastest-growing major economy, with a large and youthful population, an expanding middle class, and a diverse industrial base. Over the last decade, India has made significant progress in improving its trade infrastructure and regulatory environment. However, challenges such as bureaucratic hurdles and infrastructure deficits still exist. India's export strategy needs to focus on leveraging its strengths, such as IT services, pharmaceuticals, and textiles, while exploring new markets and opportunities within BRICS.

China is the second-largest economy in the world and a dominant player in global trade. The country has a vast manufacturing base and a growing consumer market, presenting significant opportunities for Indian exporters. However, India faces challenges in its trade relationship with China, including trade imbalances and geopolitical tensions. Developing a fine strategy to engage with China is crucial for India's long-term export goals.

South Africa serves as a gateway to the African continent, with its rich mineral resources and developed financial markets. India has increasingly engaged with South Africa, particularly in sectors like mining, manufacturing, and technology. The potential for collaboration in areas such as renewable energy and infrastructure development can enhance trade relations between the two countries.

Review of Literature

Sandeep Solanki, Krishna Murthy Inumula (2020) analyses the impact of long-run equilibrium between BRCS, SCO and ECA trade on India's economic growth. They used co-integration model for the analysis. They concluded that BRCS and SCO countries effect India's economic growth in long-run while EAC countries do not show long-run equilibrium with India.

Javeria Maryam, Ashok Mittal (2019) evaluates the comparative advantage between India and BRICS economies with the help of Bilateral Revealed Comparative Advantage Index and Trade Complementarity Index. They also used Gravity model of trade to analyze role of some selected variables. The result showed that India has comparative advantage in agricultural and manufacturing products but distance works as an obstacle in trade flows with BRICS.

Zhao Zhongxiu and Lan Qingxin (2020) discuss the trade integration within BRICS in context of trade, FDI and stock market. They try to check the effect of these variables on cooperation within BRICS. They used the data from 1990-2017 for their analysis.

Naveen Kumar and Seema Singh (2017) examines the intra-BRICS trade patterns with the Trade Intensity Index (TII) to check India's demand within BRICS countries. They observed that trade intensities of South Africa and Brazilwith India improved since 2001.

Innocents Edoun and Hews KGaphola (2017) evaluate the effect of foreign trade on BRICS and its impact on economic reforms and trade policies of India. The result showed that trade with BRICS benefit the Indian economy and help in India's GDP growth, which in turn, attract foreign investment in India.

RatnaVadra (2011) analyses the importance of BRIC on India's trade from 1999-00 to 2009-10 and also studies the transition of BRIC into BRICS. The research shows that India has positive impact of trade from BRICS countries.

Dr. R. Ramanujam and A. Kavitha (2020) evaluates the importance of international trade on India's economic growth. They study the role of foreign trade in different economic issues. They concluded that international trade is important for India's economic growth.

Nivedita Das Kundu (2001) examines the historical and contemporary trade relations between India and Russia, highlighting the cordial and friendly ties that have characterized their partnership. This study considers the impact of Russia's transition to a free market economy, which has facilitated increased trade and investment Opportunities.

Ravindra Kumar and Pavnesh Kumar (2023) identify the five leading goods with current trade trends between India and BRICS and find the obstacles that countries have been facing recently. They used the data from 2010-2022 for the analysis with the help of CAGR and SPSS software. They also evaluate the impact of FDI on India's trade.

Anand Shankar Paswan (2018) examines the trade volume of India with the other BRICS countries in the past 15 years. He tries to find the five leading commodity groups which are important

for the increase in India's trade with BRICS and also evaluates the Intra – BRICS trade pattern from year 2002 to 2017. The study reflected that BRICS nations have all means of production but due to a lack of cutting-edge technology, they did not achieve their full growth according to their potential.

Research gap

After reviewing the existing literature on India, it was found that most studies focus on India's trade relations with BRICS countries as a group. However, very few have specifically explored the trade relationship between India and Russia within BRICS, particularly in terms of how India's exports to these nations affect India's GDP. This study seeks to fill the gap by providing observations that can support policymakers in strategies to boost India's GDP by promoting trade within the BRICS group, with a special focus on India-South Africa trade.

Objectives of the study

1. To provide a summary of the trade relationship between India and BRICS nations, with focus on Russia, from 2010-11 to 2022-23.
2. To examine the impact of India's exports to BRICS nations, particularly Russia, on India's Gross Domestic Product.

Research questions

- What impact does bilateral trade with BRICS countries, particularly South Africa, have on India's Gross Domestic Product?
- How have India's exports to BRICS nations, with special emphasis on Russia, contributed to the growth of India's GDP?

Data and Methodology

This research is both descriptive and analytical, as it inspects the relationship between India's bilateral trade with BRICS countries. It relies on secondary data obtained from sources like the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Trade Organization (WTO), World Bank, and the Ministry of Commerce and Industry database. The study focuses on BRICS countries especially Russia and covers the period from 2010-11 to 2022-23.

Analysis of India's export to BRICS countries with a focus on Russia and its impact on India's GDP

India's trade relationship with Russia within the BRICS framework has seen significant changes between 2010-11 and 2023-24. During this time, India's exports to Russia have significantly increased, which has also had a very positive impact on India's GDP, highlighting diverse trade patterns.

Year	Export to Russia (in US\$ billion)	India's GDP (in US\$ billion)
2010-11	1.68	1680
2011-12	1.77	1820
2012-13	2.29	1830
2013-14	2.12	1860
2014-15	2.09	2040
2015-16	1.58	2100
2016-17	1.93	2290
2017-18	2.11	2650
2018-19	2.38	2700
2019-20	3.01	2840
2020-21	2.65	2670
2021-22	3.25	3170
2022-23	3.14	3350
2023-24	4.26	3550

Source: ministry of commerce and industry and world bank data

The above table and graph show that India's exports to Russia from 2010-11 to 2023-24, India's exports to Russia generally increased, despite some fluctuations. In 2010-11, exports stood at \$1.68 billion and reached \$4.26 billion by 2023-24. Notable increases occurred between 2011-12 and 2019-20, where exports rose from \$1.77 billion to \$3.01 billion. After a slight decline during the pandemic year of 2020-21, exports rebounded to \$3.25 billion in 2021-22 and further grew to \$4.26 billion by 2023-24, indicating a steady upward trend in trade.

Similarly, India's GDP has also seen consistent growth, rising from \$1.68 trillion in 2010-11 to \$3.55 trillion in 2023-24. The GDP saw notable jumps during the periods of 2014-15 to 2017-18 and after the pandemic recovery in 2021-22. This steady economic growth reflects India's increasing global economic influence and its deepening trade relations with Russia, although the rate of export growth has been more modest compared to the rapid rise in India's GDP.

Conclusion

In conclusion, analyzing India's trade trends with BRICS nations provides key insights into shaping a more strategic export policy for the coming decade. The steady growth in exports, despite fluctuations, underscores the potential for India to expand its market presence in these economies, particularly with Russia and China. To maximize future opportunities, India should focus on diversifying its export portfolio, strengthening partnerships, and addressing barriers to trade such as tariffs. By leveraging BRICS as a platform for collaboration, India can enhance its competitiveness, foster economic growth, and further integrate into the global trade landscape.

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